

INVESTIGATION OF PROTEIN BASED PLASTICS AND COMPOSITES FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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1 General Introduction

Processability of plant-based protein and oil plastics was investigated by extrusion, injection molding, casting and compression molding. The goal of this work was to develop formulations that could meet industrial specifications. Applications included, lubrication sticks, plant pots, chew toys and chemical delivery applications. The mechanical properties were enhanced the addition of crosslinking agents such as, phthalic anhydride and natural fibers like coconut fiber husks (CFH) and corn cobs (CC). It was observed that plastics with GTD cross-linkers and composite plastics processed with CFH exhibited superior properties. Another objective was to improve water stability of soy protein isolate (SPI) plastics by using commercial plasticizers as crosslinking modifiers. It was also found that plant oils could be crosslinked to produce plants with a wide mechanical properties, ranging hard and strong to highly flexible [1]. Composites of fibers, SPI and flours were also compounded and characterized. The costs of the flour based composite were significantly lower compared to the SPI composites and had lower mechanical properties but were still able to meet many product specifications [2].

2.0 Materials and Procedures

Soy protein isolate (SPI, ~90% protein) was obtained from Solae Company, St. Louis, MO. Plasticizer, and salts i.e. glycerol(Gly), sodium sulfite, sorbic acid (potassium salt), and potassium phosphate dibasic(D) were obtained from Fisher Scientific (Pittsburgh, PA). Chemicals Maleic anhydride (M.A), phthalic anhydride (P.A), and butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) were procured from Sigma Aldrich and Acros Organics.

Zein (90% protein) in the powder form was obtained from Global Protein Products, CA/Freeman industries. Plasticizers glycerol (reagent)

and denatured ethanol were procured from Fisher Scientific. Cross-linking compounds glyoxal trimer dihydrate $\geq 97\%$ and phthalic anhydride were obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Filler fibers, corn cobs and coconut fiber were attained from local agricultural sources. The coconut fiber utilized, was a mixture of pericarp dust and fibers from the coconut hull, the ratio of dust to fibers was not characterized and the formulations were mixed with a standard mixer. All extrusion processes were completed with a PL 2000 series single screw extruder (30" in length 1-1/4" in dia.) from C. W. Brabender® Instruments, Inc. Injection and compression Molding of ASTM standard samples was done on a 22 ton Boy injection molding machine and a 20 ton Wabash pilot compression molding Machine.

3.0 Results

3.1 Water stabilization of soy protein plastics

Soy plastics processed with anhydrides were observed to have a better water resistance in comparison with control. The water resistance of the plastics was generally proportional to the concentration of anhydrides in the plastic as seen in Fig. 1. In reference to the maleic anhydride formulations, MA 3% and MA 5% the water absorption after 24 hrs dropped from 70% to 27 % respectively. With phthalic anhydride formulations PA 3.5%, 5% and 10% the water absorption of the plastics followed a trend similar the maleic anhydride formulations. The formulation of PA 10% had water absorption value of 19% after 24hrs which was the lowest among the anhydride plastic formulations as seen in Fig. 1. It was observed that the wet strength value of PA 10% formulation was relatively more water stable compared to the other formulations,

however its tensile properties also dimensioned after 24 hrs as seen in Figure 2.

3.2 Natural fiber composites

Composite plastic formulations made with 20 Parts of corn cob fiber and with cross-linking agents, exhibited better overall mechanical properties relative (tensile strength) to the control formulation. It was observed that there was no significant difference in strength values between the different corn cobs formulations as detailed in Fig. 3.

As described in the methodology section, coconut fiber formulations were both compression and injection molded. It was observed that overall performance of injection molded samples were better than that of compression molded samples in terms of mechanical properties. From Fig. 4 it can be seen that the strength of injection molded samples were as high as 18Mpa, approximately 30% higher than that of compression molded samples. In addition it is seen that strength is proportional to the fiber loading. It is also noted that, as the strength and modulus increased with fiber loading, the extension and toughness of the composite plastics reduced by approximately 90% (in the case of toughness between CF25 & CF50)

3.3 Applications

Because of the inherent biodegradability of these materials, the applications that are best suited for these plastics are ones that have a relative short life cycle and are intended to degrade within a relatively short period time (6-18 months).

One possible product that has been considered are disposable utensils as seen in Fig. 5. These applications would not add to land fill issues and would degrade quickly after use.

All seen in the figure are golf tees. These have the addition feature of not only being biodegradable, but as we have shown, because they matrix is protein, and proteins have a

nature high nitrogen content, this product can self fertilize during degradation.

As seen in Fig. 6, it is also to make pots that can be planted with the plant so as to promote growth as the plastic will degrade and release nitrogen. The advantage of this pot design over other biodegradable materials, such as paper and moss, is that they are water proof and do not require regular water in order to assure plant growth during storage.

Other formulations are sprayable and can be applied to paper, agricultural products as seen in Fig. 7, to provide temporary, biodegradable water resistant coating.

While not fully tested, it is also envisioned that products such as animal toys could be produced from protein based plastics as seen in Fig. 8.

Other possible applications include lubrication sticks for applications where the product is used in outdoor, environmental conditions so as not to add to environmental pollutions.

Fig. 1 Water absorption of Maleic and Phthalic anhydride formulations over 24Hrs

Figure 2 Wet strength for formulations with antioxidant additives and anhydride formulations with salts over 24Hrs

Fig. 3. Strength of corn cobs formulation w and w/o cross-linking agents.

Fig. 4. Strength of Coconut fiber formulations as a function of fiber content and molding technique

Fig. 5. Photograph of utensils made from protein based plastics

Fig. 6. Photograph of pots made from protein based plastics

Fig. 7. Photograph of hay bales sprayed with protein based plastic coatings

Fig. 8. Photograph of dog toy made with protein based plastic coatings

Fig. 9. Photograph of lubrication sticks made with protein based plastic coatings

References

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